

PERSONALITY TRAITS AND TOURISM-PRENEURSHIP TENDENCY OF HOSPITALITY AND TOURISM MANAGEMENT UNDERGRADUATES

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined the relationship between the big five personality traits and tourism-preneurship tendency of undergraduate students of hospitality and tourism management, University of Port Harcourt. The study used a structured questionnaire. Multiple regressions analysis that allows for exploration of the interrelationship among sets of variables were adopted for the analysis of data collected. The researchers carefully screen the data in terms of missing values, influential outliers, normality, and multicollinearity using statistical package for social science (SPSS) software version 23 before proceeding with the analysis. The result shows that there is a positive and significant correlation between the five dimensions of personality traits and tourism-prenueurship tendency (TPI) in respect to hospitality and tourism management undergraduate students, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria except for openness to experiences. The result further validates the proposed big-five personality traits and tourism-preneurship tendency model for hospitality and tourism management undergraduate students of the University of Port Harcourt. It also confirms contentiousness as making the strongest unique contribution to tourism-preneurship tendency of hospitality and tourism management undergraduate students, University of Port Harcourt, Choba, Nigeria. This study contributed to the body of knowledge in the tourism domain by authenticating the usage of the big five personality traits for predicting tourism-entrepreneurship tendency of hospitality and tourism management students in an emerging economy. Overall, this research contributes to knowledge of universonity student's personality traits and their relations with tourism-entrepreneurship intention. It fills the gap of limited empirical studies on entrepreneurship and tourism management in emerging economies.

KEYWORDS

Personality Trait, Tourism-preneurship, Openness to Experience, Extraversion, Emotional stability.

INTRODUCTION

Hospitality and Tourism Management is a professional, vocational, and action-oriented discipline that prepares students for thinking critically and working outside existing practices and paradigms hence, essential features for fostering tourism-preneurship. Tourism-preneurship in this context implies the process of taking private initiative to identifying and converting tourism resources to tourist's products to create utility for tourists with impact on the development of the host community. Tourism-preneurship no doubt boosts the tourism economy of countries through employment and value creation (Davidsson & Wiklund, 2001; Holmgren & From, 2005). Tourism economy therefore explains all businesses that cater for the needs of the travelling public (Wall & Mathieson, 2006; Robert et al. 2010). Naido (2007) and Bardolet and Sheldon (2008) gave better insight to the meaning of tourism economy hence, defined as economy type that support businesses that focuses on the provision of products and services capable of enhancing the touristic experience of tourists while contributing towards the economic development of the host communities.

Following the suggestion of Smallbone and Welter (2012) to examine entrepreneurship intention in contrasting environments, this study therefore focuses on tourism-preneurship tendency of hospitality and tourism management students in an emerging economy with emphasis on undergraduate students of the University of Port Harcourt, South-South Nigeria.

The main questions that call for this study arose from "Why the non-professionally trained persons in hospitality and tourism management in Port Harcourt, foresee the profitable opportunities to venture into the businesses of hospitality and tourism but, the professionally trained once do not"? This research question is validated by our recent observation of trends of tourism-preneurial practices in Port Harcourt. We observed that a significant part of private businesses in hospitality and tourism sector in the city were established by the non-professionals in the discipline! We therefore argue that in spite of better hospitality and tourism management education, and access to new venture finance, hospitality and tourism management graduates in Port Harcourt, South-South Nigeria have low level of tourism-preneurship tendency.

Previous studies had examined different factors that influence the intensity of intentions. Pillis & Reardon, (2007) question the extent to which traits can be used to predict the intention to start a business. Personality traits provide insight whether a person will be able to do a particular business or not. Studies have shown that people's personality traits determine how they react to the environment (Dabrowski, 2008; Liao & Lee, 2009). Hisrich et al. (2007) also argued that the role of personality traits could have been underestimated in past entrepreneurship research due to design and methodological limitations. It is pertinent to state that limited attempt had been made to examine the link between personality traits and tourism-preneurship intention behaviour among hospitality and tourism management students in emerging economies and Nigeria in particular. Filling this gap call for this study hence, the study aims to determine the relationship between each of the big five personality traits and tourism-preneurship tendency in respect to hospitality and tourism management undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt, South-South, Nigeria. University of Port Harcourt is chosen for this study because the institution is the only federal university in south-south Nigeria that offers hospitality and tourism management as an academic discipline. Aside, the university is an entrepreneurship university.

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

Personality Traits

Different personality theorists present own definitions of personality traits based on their theoretical positions. Golpayegan (2017) defined personality traits as the combination of constant mental and physical features which gives identity to individuals. Dabrowski (2008) defined personality traits as the totality of psychological and physical dispositions of an individual. AkinboyeandSoaib (2016) referred to personality traits as the behavioural patterns which are developed mainly during decisive years. Crage (2013) sees personality traits as the structures and propensities that explain individual's characteristic patterns of thought, emotion and behaviour and recurring regularities or trends in him/her. Personality traits encompass a person's relative stable feelings, thoughts, and behavioral patterns that differentiate people from others (Barge, 2014). Personality traits are tendencies of individuals to behave in similar ways across settings and situations (Ones et al.,2005). Personality traits is seen as dynamic and organised set of characteristics possessed by an individual that uniquely influences his or her behavior, cognitions and motivations in various situations (Ryckman, 2004). Personal traits explain different characteristics that can contribute to inferences about behavioral results (Liao & Lee, 2009). It explains those behaviours which differentiates one person from another person (Beer & Brooks, 2011). Personality traits is defined as the individual pattern of psychological processes arising from individual characteristics such as patterns of thought, emotion, behaviour, motives, and feeling (Pandey &KaviTha, 2015). Personality traits explains the individual's unique, typical and preferred way of feeling, thinking and behaving (Zahari, 2016). The index in these definitions shows that personality trait is an emotional pattern that influences once decisions.

Tourism-preneurshipTendency

Tourism-preneurship tendency is the process of identifying and exploiting tourism business opportunities through invention and innovation thereby creating new and or improved tourist products and services capable utility to tourists (Thomas & Mueller, 2000). The term can as well be defined as intentions of individuals to be self-employed by establishing their own tourism business or by buying an established one (Khan, 2013; Nosheena et al., 2019). Entrepreneurship intention is the individuals' conscious plan and action to set up a new tourism business venture in today or near future (Tong et al., 2011; Bosma et al., 2012). Furthermore, entrepreneurship tendency is seen as the individual's willingness to start a new tourism firm or create new value for the existing tourism organisation (Thomas & Mueller, 2000). In addition, tourism-preneurship tendency is seen as effort of a person(s) to act entrepreneurially by establishing tourism business. Hmieleski& Corbett (2006) believe that tourism-preneurshiptendency is an intention to establish a high-growth tourism related business. Pruet (2012) opined that tourism-preneurshiptendency are plans to pursue tourism business ownership careers. Tourism-preneurshiptendency is self-acknowledged conviction by a person that they intend to set up a new tourism related business venture and consciously plan to do so at some point in the future (Thompson, 2009; Ridha & Wahyu, 2017). Choo and Wong (2009) described tourism-preneurshiptendency as the exploration and assessment of information which is beneficial to achieve the objective of tourism business creation. The index in the above information opined that tourism-preneurship tendency is seen as the process of creating new tourist venture by dedicating the necessary time and effort; assuming the financial and social risk, and receiving the monetary rewards, personal satisfaction and independence.

THEORETICAL UNDERLINING: THE BIG FIVE PERSONALITY MODEL

The big five personality model is one of the wide-ranging and most used applied personality taxonomies (Costa & McCrae, 1992) in behavioral science. Goldberg (1981) proposed and used the big five personality model to demarcate five factors which include: emotional stability, conscientiousness, agreeableness, extraversion, and openness to experience to explain individual's personality. These five personality traits that describe personality is commonly referred to as the big five personality trait. Various studies had used the model to provide a general basis for examining the correlation between personality traits and the tendency to become an entrepreneur (Barrick & Mount, 1991; Zhao & Seibert, 2006; Rauch & Frese, 2007). Conscientiousness construct in the model is associated with trait adjectives such as dependable, organized, reliable, ambitious, hardworking (Brice, 2004; Major et al., 2006; Zhao & Seibert, 2006; Zhao et al., 2010), while agreeableness has adjectives such as kind, cooperative, sympathetic, helpful, courteous, and warm (Brice, 2004; Zhao & Seibert, 2006; Zhao et al., 2010). On the other hand, emotional stability has to do with nervous, moody, emotional, insecure, and unstable character (Zhao & Seibert, 2006; Zhao, 2010; Méndez-Picazo, 2012). Openness to experience has to do with curious, imaginative, creative, complex, refined, sophisticated (Brice, 2004, Major et al., 2006, Zhao & Seibert, 2006; Zhao et al., 2010), while extraversion is associated with adjective traits such as talkative, sociable, passionate, bold, dominant (Major et al., 2006; Zhao & Seibert, 2006; Zhao et al., 2010). As it applied to the current study, the big five personality model is being used to explain the connection between each of the five personality traits and tourism-preneurship tendency of hospitality management and tourism undergraduates, University of Port Harcourt, Choba, Nigeria.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Extraversion and Tourism-preneurship Tendency

Extraversion is the expression of extrovertly characteristics such as assertiveness, talkativeness, sociability, and ambition (Barrick & Mount, 1991). Extraversion according to Shane (2003) is a treasured trait for entrepreneurs because they are characterized with spending a lot of time interacting with investors, employees, and customers. In a study of psychological test measuring extraversion at age 11 of people who were born in one week in March 1958 in Britain indicated that those who went into business themselves in adulthood had higher extraversion scores when they were children. Correspondingly, the National Longitudinal Survey of Youths in the United States showed that being outgoing as a child predicts working for one's self in adulthood (Van Praag & Ophem, 1995). Mei et al. (2017) examined the relationships between the Big Six personality traits and entrepreneurship intention, inclusive of the mediating role of entrepreneurial self-efficacy of college students in the Chinese context. The study reveals that extraversion has a significant connection with entrepreneurial intention. Howard & Howard (1995) found that the entrepreneurial-type person can be categorized as scoring high on extraversion personality trait. Other empirical investigation that agrees with the correlation between extraversion and entrepreneurship tendency include Shane (2003) who opined that there is positive and significant relationship between extraversion trait and entrepreneurship tendency.

Base on the reviews above we argue that empirical study targeted to determining the correlation between extraversion and tourism-preneurship tendency of undergraduate students of hospitality and tourism management in an entrepreneurial university in an emerging economy and the University of Port Harcourt in particular are limited. On the footing of this, we propose the following hypothesis:

H₁: Extraversion trait has a positive and significant relationship with tourism-preneurship tendency of undergraduate students of hospitality and tourism management, University of Port Harcourt.

Agreeableness and Tourism-preneurship Tendency

The agreeableness dimension refers to an individual's tendency to defer to others. It explains traits of persons who are supportive, credulous, magnanimous, easy-going, considerate and soft-hearted (Barrick & Mount, 1991). Empirical research findings confirm conflicting evidence on the association between agreeableness trait and entrepreneurship tendency. While some reported a negative connection between the two constructs, others reported otherwise (Goldberg, 1990; Zhao & Seibert, 2006; Antoncic et al., 2015). Evidences of some empirical studies shows that agreeable people are more likely to go back to traditional employment through outplacement if laid off than starting own business. Zhao & Seibert (2006) in their meta-analysis of several studies in the domain of personality traits and entrepreneurship tendency showed that entrepreneurs scored lower than managers on agreeableness. Mei et al. (2017) examined the relationships between the Big Six personality and entrepreneurial intention, inclusive of the mediating role of entrepreneurial self-efficacy of college students in the Chinese context. The study reveals that agreeableness had no effect on entrepreneurial intention. Antoncic et al. (2015) in their study of personality traits of people in employment in Slovenia found that persons with agreeableness traits, are compassionate, sincere, kind and supportive hence, less likely to become entrepreneurs or have an intention to become entrepreneurs.

On the other hand, Goldberg (1990) opined that agreeableness traits relates to entrepreneurship. In his study, he identified agreeableness items such as cooperation, being helpful, patient, cordial, friendliness, trustful, and diplomatic as attributes of entrepreneurs. Antoncic et al. (2015) in their study of personality traits of people in employment in Slovenia established some sign of the influence of the agreeableness trait on entrepreneurship. Thus, opined that agreeableness factor includes traits that can be related to entrepreneurship. The implication of these reviews shows that agreeable people may or may not start businesses. This validates the possible ambiguity in the agreeableness factor (Ryckman 2004). Howard & Howard (1995) viewed the entrepreneur-type as having average scores on agreeableness hence, no clear correlation can be established between agreeableness and entrepreneurship.

On the basis of this, we argue that since empirical evidence on the connection between agreeableness construct and tourism-preneurship tendency in respect to undergraduate students of hospitality and tourism management, University of Port Harcourt is limited, we therefore propose the following hypothesis:

H₂: Agreeableness trait has a positive and significant relationship with tourism-preneurship tendency of undergraduate students of hospitality and tourism management, University of Port Harcourt.

Emotional Stability and Tourism-preneurship Tendency

Emotional stable people are described as people who are calm, stable, even-tempered, and hardy (Barrick & Mount, 1991; Zhao & Seibert, 2006; Zhao, 2010; Méndez-Picazo, 2012). Theoretically, persons with high emotional stability are not easily disturbed by negative factors, even in some stressful situations. Emotional stability may be a trait that is important for entrepreneurial success (Barrick et al., 2001; Rauch & Frese 2007). Entrepreneurs are characteristically described as resilience, optimistic, and stable in the face of social pressure, and indecision (Locke & Baum, 2007). A variety of studies show that people high on emotional stability are more likely than others to engage in

entrepreneurship (Zhao & Seibert, 2006). The findings of Goldberg (1990) opined that emotionally stable people tend to be characterized by self-sufficiency, individuality, and distinctiveness hence, attributes that are essential for a successful entrepreneurship. Indeed, autonomy or independence may be related to entrepreneurship serving as an important motivator (Licht & Siegel 2006). Bandura (1997) argue that individuals who have high levels of emotional stability could break through the dilemma when they are confronted with unfriendly situations, and have a positive attitude or evaluation toward their innovation ability (John et al., 2008), thereby forming higher entrepreneurial self-efficacy. Another study showed that people who had founded their own businesses were more emotionally stable as measured by Catell's 16PF (Brandstetter, 1997). Rauch & Freese (2007) reports that people who are emotionally stable are more likely to start their own businesses because entrepreneurs need a high tolerance to stress to cope with the hard work, significant risks, social isolation, pressure, insecurity, and personal financial difficulties associated with starting new businesses (Rauch & Freese, 2007). Entrepreneurs cannot worry excessively, and need to be resilient in the face of setbacks when building a company (Zhao & Siebert, 2006). Since empirical evidence on the link between agreeableness construct and tourism-preneurship tendency in respect to undergraduate students of hospitality and tourism management, University of Port Harcourt is limited, we therefore propose the following hypothesis:

H₃: Emotional Stability has a positive and significant relationship with tourism-preneurship tendency of undergraduate students of hospitality and tourism management, University of Port Harcourt.

Openness to Experience and Tourism-preneurship Tendency

Opportunity recognition researchers has stressed the importance of openness to experience attribute to entrepreneurship tendency (Pech & Cameron 2006; Alvarez & Barney 2007; Baron 2007). People with obvious openness personality have open minds about new things, and are willing to innovate (John et al., 2008). Individuals who score high in openness to experience are more likely to be intellectually curious, imaginative, and creative hence, attributes that are related to opportunity recognition (Goldberg 1990; Ryckman 2000). Several studies that explore the correlation between entrepreneurship and personality found that openness to experience is a significant factor (Howard & Howard 1995; Singh & De Noble 2003; Zhao & Seibert, 2006). Antoncic et al. (2015) in their study of personality traits of people in employment in Slovenia found that entrepreneurs tend to have higher levels of openness to experience trait. Mei et al. (2017) investigated the associations between the Big Six personality traits and entrepreneurial intention of Chinese college students. The study reveals that openness to experience is significantly positively correlated with entrepreneurial intention. Xu & Guo (2015) examined the relationship between entrepreneurial stress, entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intention of vocational college students. The outcome of the study shows a strong and significant relationship between openness to experience and entrepreneurship tendency. Wang et al. (2016) studied the contribution of self-efficacy to the relationship between personality traits and entrepreneurial intention of agriculture students in Asia Pacific rural areas. The outcome of the study shows a positive associated between openness to experience and entrepreneurship tendency. Peterson & Whiteman (2007) examined the interrelations among self-assessed acumen, self-concept, self-efficacy and the personality trait brain power of university students in Scotland and New Zealand. The study validates a positive connection between openness to experience and entrepreneurship tendency.

Base on the reviews above we contend that empirical study targeted to determining the link between openness to experience personality trait and tourism-preneurship tendency of undergraduate

students of hospitality and tourism management, university of Port Harcourt has not been reported. On this ground, we propose the following hypothesis:

H₄: Openness to Experience has a positive and significant relationship with tourism-preneurship tendency of undergraduate students of hospitality and tourism management, university of Port Harcourt.

Conscientiousness and Tourism-preneurship Tendency

Ryckman (2004) opined that “Will to Achieve” can be used as an alternate label for “Conscientiousness” This implies that conscientious people tend to be efficient (Goldberg1990), deliberate (John 1990), organized, and systematic (Goldberg 1990).Conscientious people care more about achievement and advancement; they focus more attention on the perfect combination of individual’s goals and collective goals; they are careful toward their work, and could master what they are doing or responsible for (John et al., 2008). Empirical evidences confirmed positive association between conscientiousness and the tendency to be an entrepreneur (Zhao & Siebert, 2006; Antoncic et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2016). Howard & Howard (1995) found that people with high conscientious trait exhibits characteristic of an entrepreneur. Zhao & Seibert (2006) concluded that conscientiousness has the strongest relationship to the entrepreneurship status among the big five personality factors. Luthans &Ibrayeva (2006) studied the entrepreneurial self-efficacy in central Asian emerging economies using numerical and qualitative analyses. The result shows that conscientiousness is related to entrepreneurship tendency. Sun & Zhang (2014) examined the path model of the relationship of personality traits, entrepreneurial self-efficacy, and entrepreneurial intention among college students. The outcome of the study validates positive connection between conscientiousness and entrepreneurship tendency.

In view of these reviews, we argue that empirical study that determined the connection between conscientiousness and tourism-preneurship tendency of undergraduate students of hospitality and tourism management, university of Port Harcourt is limited thus, the following hypothesis:

H₅: Conscientiousness has a positive and significant relationship with tourism-preneurship tendency of undergraduate students of hospitality and tourism management, university of Port Harcourt.

OPERATIONAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE STUDY

The big-five personality traits and tourism-preneurshiptendency model for hospitality management and tourism students, university of Port-Harcourt is projected for this study as shown in Figure 1. The model displaysthe five personality traits as independent variable and tourism-preneurship tendency as the dependent variable. The independent variable is measured by five dimensions: Extraversion, Agreeableness, Emotional stability, Openness to experience, and Conscientiousness. The model is expected to explain the relationship between the five personality traits and the dependent variable (i.e., Tourism-preneurship Tendency) in respect to hospitality and tourism management students in the University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria

Figure 1: The Big-five Personality Traits and Tourism-prenurship Tendency Model for Hospitality Management and Tourism Students.

Source: (Authors' Conceptualization, 2020)

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a survey research design to establish the correlation between personality traits and tourism-prenurship tendency in the context of hospitality and tourism management students, university of Port Harcourt, Choba, Nigeria. A Five-dimensional personality traits scale developed by Adeola et al. (2017) were adopted and modified into a 26 items scale (Extraversion- 6 items; Openness to experience- 5 items; Agreeableness-5 items; Conscientiousness, 5 items, and emotional stability-5 items). Also, a five items scale of Tendency to become Entrepreneur adopted from (Leong, 2008; Liñán& Chen, 2009) were modified to develop 8 items Tourism-prenueurship Intention (TPI) scale used for this study. The questionnaire has three sections; section 1 contains the respondent's bio data such as age, marital status, gender, religion etc. Section 2 contains five dimensions of personality trait, and section 3 contains 8 items measures of tourism-prenurship tendency structured on a five (5) point likert scale with weights assigned as follows: 5 -strongly agree, 4 - agree, 3 – neutral, 2- disagree, and 1 – strongly disagree.

The research population for this study comprised of 100- 400 level degree students of the Department of Hospitality and Tourism Management, University of Port Harcourt who are currently enrolled in the 2019/20 academic session, totaling 461. However, since it is practically impossible for the researchers to sample the entire population of the students in the Department of Hospitality and Tourism Management, the researchers determined the proportion of the sample unit that constitutes the sample. This was done by aligning with the method of proportional allocation as suggested in Kothari (1990). The concept suggests that the sizes of samples from different strata are kept

propositional to the sizes of the strata. Therefore, Taro Yamane formula was applied to determine the sample size (n) as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Observation Unit of Hospitality and Tourism Management Undergraduate Students, 2019/20 Academic Session.

Institution	Level of Programme	Number of Enrolled Students	Sample Size
University of Port Harcourt	100	145	67
	200	70	33
	300	96	45
	400	150	70
Total		461	215

Source (Researchers Computation, 2020).

The researchers personally administered structured questionnaires to the students at various level of their programme of study until the sample size of 215 is met. Pearson moment correlation analysis that allows the exploration of the interrelationship among a set of variables (Pallant, 2010) were adopted for the analysis of data collected. Before proceeding with the analysis of objectives in the present study, the researchers carefully screen the data in terms of missing values, influential outliers, normality, and multicollinearity using statistical package for social science (SPSS) software version 23.

RESULTS

Demographic Distribution of Respondents

The gender distribution of the respondents indicates that 64.2% of the respondents are males and 35.8% are females. This implied that majority of the participants in this study are males. In terms of marital status, 68.8% of the respondents are single, 29.8% are married, and .1.4% are divorced. This implied that majority of the participants in this study are single, followed by the married. The religion distribution of respondents used in the present study includes: Christianity (75.3%), Islam (14.9%) and Others (9.8%). This shows that majority of participants in this study are Christians followed by Muslims with only very few Other's participants.

Reliability Analysis

The outcome of the reliability analysis shows that each of the five personality traits has a Cronbach's alpha readings as follows; Openness to experience, ($\alpha=.799$), Conscientiousness, ($\alpha=.819$), Extraversion, ($\alpha=.862$), Agreeableness, ($\alpha=.851$), and Emotional stability, ($\alpha=.806$). The Cronbach's alpha readings of the dependent variable- Tourism-PreneurshipTendency, ($\alpha=.767$). These results justify that all the items of the five personality traits, and the dependent variable- Tourism-PreneurshipTendencyin respect to hospitality and tourism management undergraduate students, university of Port Harcourt, Nigeria has Cronbach's alpha value $>.70$. This shows the internally consistency of the items in the instrument (Hair et al. 2006).

Correlations of Personality Traits and Tourism-Preneuriship Tendency

Data collected were analysed using Pearson moment correlation to determine the relationship between personality traits and Tourism-Preneurship Tendency in respect to hospitality and tourism management undergraduate students, university of Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The result is shown in Table 1.

Table 2: Correlations of Personality Traits and Tourism-Preneurship Tendency

Variables	R	P	Level
Tourism-Preneurship Tendency(TPI)	--	--	--
Openness to Experience (OPE)	0.056	0.208	Medium
Extraversion (EXV)	0.252	0.000	Low
Agreeableness (AGR)	0.171	0.006	Low
Emotional stability (EMS)	0.314	0.000	Medium
Conscientiousness (CON)	0.267	0.000	Low

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: (Authors Computation, 2020).

The results as shown in Table 2 depicted that there is positive and significant correlation between the five dimensions of personality traits and tourism-preneurship tendency (TPI) in respect to hospitality and tourism management undergraduate students, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria except for Openness to experiences: Extraversion (EXV) ($r = 0.252$; $p = 0.000$), Agreeableness (AGR) ($r = 0.171$; $p = 0.006$), Emotional stability (EMS) ($r = 0.314$; $p = 0.000$), Conscientiousness (CON) ($r = 0.267$; $p = 0.000$), and Openness to Experience (OPE) ($r = 0.056$; $p = 0.208$). In terms of the strength of the relationship, the results shown that Extraversion (EXV) ($r = 0.252$), Agreeableness (AGR) ($r = 0.171$), and Conscientiousness has low and positive relationship while Emotional stability (EMS) ($r = 0.314$) has a medium and positive relationship. Therefore, the alternate hypothesis was accepted which states that there is a significant and positive relationship between extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness and emotional stability and tourism-preneurship tendency (TPI) in respect to hospitality and tourism management undergraduate students, university of Port Harcourt, Nigeria. However, we fail to accept the alternate hypothesis in respect to openness to experience.

Table 3: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.347 ^a	.120	.099	5.375	.120	5.712	5	209	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), CON, OPE, AGR, EMS, EXV

b. Dependent Variable: HOTC

Source: (Authors Computation, 2020).

From Table 3, it was depicted that the value of R-square is .120. This indicates that the goodness of fit of the Big-five Personality Traits and Tourism-preneurship Tendency Model for Hospitality and Tourism Management undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt, is statistically significant. The adjusted R-square value of .999 is also statistically significant which indicate that after taking into accounts; the number of regressors, the Big-five Personality Traits and Tourism-preneurship Tendency Model explains about 99% of the variation in Tourism-preneurship Tendency of hospitality and tourism management undergraduate students of the University of Port Harcourt, Choba, Nigeria. Thus, the remaining 1% is due to other factors and residuals. Also, the multiple R ($R = .347$) revealed a medium correlation between independent variables (i.e., Personality Traits) and

the dependent variable (i.e.,Tourism-preneurship Tendency) in respect to Hospitality Management and Tourism undergraduate students of the University of Port Harcourt.

Table 4: ANOVAa

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	824.981	5	164.996	5.712	.000b
	Residual	6037.177	209	28.886		
	Total	6862.158	214			

a. Dependent Variable: TPI

b. Predictors: (Constant), CON, OPE, AGR, EMS, EXV

Source: (Authors Computation, 2020).

From Table 4, the result of the analysis shows that F value was significant (p=.000). This shows that the model was valid. Thus, it can be concluded that there is a linear relationship between the fivepersonality traits, and Tourism-preneurship Tendency of hospitality and tourism management undergraduate students, University of Port Harcourt, Choba, Nigeria.

Table 5: Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	12.448	2.589		4.809	.000
	OPE	-.085	.124	-.049	-.680	.497
	EXV	-.915	.635	-.698	-1.441	.151
	AGR	-.111	.130	-.074	-.848	.398
	EMS	.322	.112	.252	2.880	.004
	CON	1.371	.787	.869	1.741	.083

a. Dependent Variable: TPI

Source: (Authors Computation, 2020).

From Table 5, in comparing the contribution of each independent variable, Beta values are used. As illustrated in the standardized coefficient column, Contentiousness makes the strongest unique contribution to Tourism-preneurship Tendency of hospitality and tourism management undergraduate students, University of Port Harcourt, Choba, Nigeria with ($\beta = .869$), followed by extraversion(EXV) with ($\beta = .698$), emotional stability(EMS) with ($\beta = .252$), agreeableness (AGR) made the fourth relative contribution, ($\beta = -.074$) while openness to experience made the least relative contribution ($\beta = -.049$).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study sought to establish the relationship between the big five personality traits, and Tourism-preneurship Tendency of hospitality and tourism management undergraduate students, University of Port Harcourt, Choba, Nigeria. The major findings for each objective are as follows.

Regarding the relationship between extraversion and tourism-preneurship tendency of hospitality and tourism management undergraduate students, University of Port Harcourt, Choba, the study found a positive and significant relationship. This finding corresponds with existing literatures. Mei et al. (2017) reports that extraversion has a significant connection with entrepreneurship intention. Howard & Howard (1995) found that the entrepreneurial-type person can be categorized as scoring

high on extraversion personality trait. Shane (2003) opined that there is positive and significant relationship between extraversion and entrepreneurship tendency.

Furthermore, on the relationship existing between agreeableness and tourism-preneurship tendency of hospitality and tourism management undergraduate students, University of Port Harcourt, Choba, the study found a positive and significant relationship. This finding agrees with Goldberg (1990) who opined that agreeableness relates to entrepreneurship. Antoncic et al. (2015) opined that agreeableness factor includes traits that can be related to entrepreneurship. Howard and Howard (1995) viewed the entrepreneur-type as scoring average on agreeableness.

In addition, the objective that examined the relationship between emotional stability and tourism-preneurship tendency of hospitality and tourism management undergraduate students, University of Port Harcourt, Choba, found a positive and significant relationship. This finding agrees with previous studies that people high on emotional stability are more likely than others to engage in entrepreneurship (Zhao & Seibert, 2006). Rauch and Freese (2007) reports that people who are emotionally stable are more likely to start their own businesses. Goldberg (1990) opined that emotionally stable people tend to be characterized by autonomy, independence, and individualism hence, attributes that are essential for a successful entrepreneurship.

Once again, the objective that examined the relationship between openness to experience and tourism-preneurship tendency of hospitality and tourism management undergraduate students, University of Port Harcourt, Choba, were found to be insignificant. This finding disagrees with some existing literature. Peterson & Whiteman (2007) study validates a positive connection between openness to experience and entrepreneurship tendency. Wang et al. (2016) reports a positive associated between openness to experience and entrepreneurship tendency. Xu and Guo (2015) shows a strong and significant relationship between openness to experience and entrepreneurship tendency. The fifth objective that examine the relationship between conscientious and tourism-preneurship tendency of hospitality and tourism management undergraduate students, University of Port Harcourt, Choba, were found to be significant. This finding agrees with previous empirical evidences (Antoncic et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2016). Howard and Howard (1995) found that high conscientiousness can be a characteristic of the entrepreneurial-driven person. Zhao & Seibert (2006) concluded that conscientiousness has the strongest relationship to the entrepreneurship status among the big five personality factors.

Finally, the sixth objective which determined the personality trait that mostly predicts tourism-preneurship tendency of hospitality and tourism management undergraduate students, University of Port Harcourt, Choba, found that contentiousness makes the strongest unique contribution followed by extraversion, emotional stability, agreeableness, and openness to experience made the least relative contribution.

CONCLUSIONS

The big five personality traits can potentially be used for predicting tourism-entrepreneurship start-ups by hospitality and tourism management students in an emerging economy. Other conclusions that could be drawn from this study is that hospitality and tourism management undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt who are outgoing, sociable, and generate a lot of enthusiasm stand the chances of being a tourism-preneur. In addition, a student who has the attribute of cooperating with others, forgiving in nature, unselfish, and accept other's view has the possibility of becoming a tourism-preneur. Finally, being emotionally stable, not easily upset, efficient

mindfulness, perseverance, plan-oriented, and reliability are tangible attributes of students that may likely become a tourismpreneurs.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study has implications for research, practice, and policy hence, recommended that authorities of the University of Port Harcourt and other critical stakeholders in the curriculum development domain should give more attention to domesticating organizational behavioural courses in the curriculum of hospitality and tourism management study. This in our view will help students discover their personality traits and its applicability to tourismpreneurs development. Also, the government of Nigeria in collaboration with national university commission (NUC), and the private sector should aggressively invest more on training experts in behavioral domain. This will help to ensuring that seasoned experts capable of providing the much-needed mentoring services for undergraduate students in hospitality and tourism management is sufficiently available. In addition, the government of Nigeria is strongly encouraged to invest in tourismpreneurs education by way of inclusion of tourismpreneurs management in the curriculum of students studying for hospitality and tourism. It is also recommended that individuals and institutions making considerations about financing tourismpreneurial ventures should as a matter of policy validate the personality-based tourismpreneurs potential of the applicants.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Despite the insightful results, one of the major limitations of this study is that only the undergraduate students of hospitality and tourism management students at the university of Port Harcourt was focused, thus, did not consider postgraduate students and students of other universities that offer hospitality and tourism management across Nigeria. If this is done it may provide a more in-depth insight and more meaningful results.

REFERENCES

- Adeola, A., Waliu, S. B., Adewale, A. O., Opeyemi, O. D., John, O. A. (2017). Influence of Personality Traits and Work Commitment on Job Performance of Public Secondary School Teachers in Oyo South Senatorial District of Oyo State, Nigeria. *International journal of Rural Development, Environment and Health Research*, 1, (1), 68-79.
- Akinboye, A.K. and Soaib, A. (2016). Factors affecting entrepreneurial self-efficacy of engineering students. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 6, (11), 12-17.
- Alvarez, S. A., and Barney, J. B . (2007). Discovery and Creation: Alternative Theories of Entrepreneurial Action. *Strategic Entrepreneurship Journal*, 1, 11–26.
- Antoncic, B., Bratkovic, T. K., Singh, G., and DeNoble, A. F. (2015). The Big Five Personality–Entrepreneurship Relationship: Evidence from Slovenia. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 53,(3), 819–841 .
- Bandura, A. (1997). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychology Review*, 84, 191–215.
- Bardolet, E., and Sheldon, P. (2008). Tourism in archipelagos: Hawaii and the Balearics. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 35, (4), 900-923.
- Barge, A. (2014). Expatriate performance in Overseas Assignments: The Role of Big Five Personality. *Asian Social Science*, 6, (9), 104-109.
- Baron, R. A. (2007). Behavioral and cognitive factors in entrepreneurship. *Strategic Entrepreneurship Journal*, 1, 167-182.
- Baron, R. A. (2007). Behavioral and Cognitive Factors in Entrepreneurship: Entrepreneurs as the Active Element in New Venture Creation. *Strategic Entrepreneurship Journal*, 1, 167–182.
- Barrick, M. R., and Mount, M. K. (1991). The Big Five personality dimensions and job performance: A meta-analysis. *Personnel Psychology*, 44, 1–26.
- Barrick, M. R., Mount, M. K., and Judge, T. A. (2001). The FFM Personality Dimensions and Job-Performance: Meta-Analysis of MetaAnalyses. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*, 9, 9–30.
- Beer, A., & Brooks, C. (2011). Information quality in personality judgment: The value of personal disclosure. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 45, (2), 175-185.
- Bosma, N. (2012). *GEM Manual: A report on the design, data and quality control of the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor*. London: GERA.
- Brandstetter, H. (1997). Becoming an entrepreneur– a question of personality structure? *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 18, 157-177.
- Brice, J. (2004). *The Role of Personality Dimensions on the Formation of Entrepreneurial Intentions*. NY, USA: Hofstra University: New York.
- Choo, Y and Wong, U. (2009). Entrepreneurial intention: Triggers and barriers to new venture creation in Singapore. *Singapore Management Review*, 28, (2), 10-16.
- Costa, P. T., Jr., and McCrae, R. R. (1992). *Revised NEO Personality Inventory (NEO-PI-R) and NEO Five Factor Inventory NEO-FFI) professional manual*. Odessa, FL: PAR.

- Crage, H. (2013). *Work Environment Factors and Job Performance: The Construction Project Manager's Perspective*. Retrieved from Degree Thesis, Universiti Sains Malaysia, Penang, Malaysia: eprints.usm.my/16071/1/Arman_Abdul_Razak.pdf.
- Dabrowski, C.J. (2008). The Big Five Personality Traits and Individual Job Performance Growth Trajectories in Maintenance and Transitional Job Stages. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 89, (5), 835–853.
- Davidsson, P. and Wiklund, J. (2001). Levels of analysis in entrepreneurship research: Current research practice and suggestions for the future. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 25, (4), 81-100.
- Goldberg, I. R. (1990). An Alternate description of personality: The big five factor structure. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 59, 1216-1229.
- Goldberg, L. R. (1981). Language and Individual Differences: The Search for Universals in Personality Lexicons. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 59, 141–165.
- Golpayegan, M. (2017). Evaluating the relation between personality properties with job satisfaction of the staff. *Journal of History Culture and Art Research*, 6, (3), 937-949.
- Hisrich, D. R, Langan-Fox, J., and Grant, S. (2007). Entrepreneurship research and practice: A call to action for psychology. *American Psychologist*, 62, (6), 575-589.
- Hmieleski, K.M. and Corbett, A.C. (2006). Proclivity for improvisation as a predictor of entrepreneurial intentions. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 44,(1),45-63.
- Holloway, C., Humphreys, C., & Davidson, R. (2009). *The Business of Tourism. 8th Edition*. Essex: Pearson Education Limited.
- Holmgren, C and From, J. (2005). Taylorism of the mind: Entrepreneurship education from a perspective of educational research. *European educational research journal*, 4, (4), 382-390.
- Howard, P. J., and Howard, J. M. (1995). *The Big Five quickstart: An introduction to the five factor model of personality for human resource professionals*. Charlotte, NC : Center for Applied Cognitive Studies.
- John, O. P. (1990). The “big five” factor taxonomy: Dimensions of personality in the natural language and questionnaires. In L. A. Pervin, *Handbook of Personality* (pp. 66-100). New York: Guilford Press.
- John, O.P., Naumann, L.P., and Soto, C.J. (2008). Paradigm shift to the integrative Big Five trait taxonomy: History, measurement, and conceptual issues. In O.P. John, R.W. Robins, & L. A. Pervin, *Handbook of Personality: Theory and Research, 3rd ed* (pp. 114-158). New York: Guilford Press.
- Khan, K. (2013). Empirical Analysis of Entrepreneurial Intentions. A case of Kabul based business students, Afghanistan. *International Journal of Information, Business and Management*, 5, (1), 184-197.
- Kothari, C. (1990). *New Age Research Methodology; Methods and Techniques (2nd Ed)*. New Delhi: New Age International (P) Limited.
- Leong, C.K. (2008). *Entrepreneurial intention: An empirical study among Open University Malaysia students: Dissertation*. Malaysia: Open University Malaysia Center for Graduate Studies.
- Liao, C. S. and Lee, C. W. (2009). An Empirical Study of employee Job Involvement and Personality Traits: The Case of Taiwan. *International Journal of Economics and Management*, 3, (1), 22-36.
- Licht, A. N., and Siegel, J. I. (2006). The Social Dimensions of Entrepreneurship. In M. Casson, B. Yeung, A. Basu, & N. Wadson, *The Oxford Handbook of Entrepreneurship. Eds* (pp. 511–539). Oxford: Oxford University Press.

- Liñán, F., and Chen, Y.W. (2009). Development and cross-cultural application of a specific instrument to measure entrepreneurial intentions. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 33, (3): 593-617.
- Locke, E., and Baum, R. (2007). Entrepreneurial motivation. In J. Baum , M. Frese , & R. Baron, *The Psychology of Entrepreneurship* (pp. 41-65). Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum.
- Luthans, F., and Ibrayeva, E.S. (2006). Entrepreneurial self-efficacy in central Asian transition economies: Quantitative and qualitative analyses. *Journal of International Business Study*, 37, 92–110.
- Major, D.A.; Turner, J.E. and Fletcher, T.D. (2006). Linking proactive personality and the Big Five to motivation to learn and development activity. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 91, 927–935.
- Mei, H., Zicheng, M., Shiwen, J., Xiaoyu, C., Xinyue, L., & Zehui, Z. (2017). The Sustainable Personality in Entrepreneurship: The Relationship between Big Six Personality, Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy, and Entrepreneurial Intention in the Chinese Context. *Sustainability*, 9, 1-23.
- Méndez-Picazo, M,T., Galindo-Martín, M, A., and Ribeiro-Soriano, D. (2012). Governance, entrepreneurship and economic growth. *Entrep. Reg. Development*, 24, 865–877.
- Naido, V. (2007). Research on the Flow of International students to UK Universities: Determinants and Implications. *Journal of Research in International Education*, 6, (3) 287-307.
- Nosheena et al. (2019). Impact of Personality Traits On Entrepreneurial Intention and Demographic Factors as Moderator. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 23, (1),1-20.
- Ones, D. S., Viswesvaran, C., & Dilchert, S. (2005). Personality at work: Raising awareness and correcting misconceptions. Cited in Noraini binti et al (2015) Association between Personality Traits and Job Performance among Secondary School Teachers . *International Academic Research Journal of Social Science*, 1, (2), 1-6.
- Pallant, J. (2010). *SPSS Survival Manual: A Step by Step Guide to Data Analysis Using SPSS*. McGraw-Hill International.
- Pandey, N.S. and Kavitha, M. (2015). Relationship between Teachers' Personality Traits and Self Efficacy: An Empirical Analysis of School Teacher in Karaikal Region. *Pacific Business Review International*, 8, (3),37-42.
- Pech, R. J., and Cameron, C. (2006). An Entrepreneurial Decision Process Model Describing Opportunity Recognition. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 9, (1), 61–78.
- Peterson, E.R., and Whiteman, M.C. (2007). “I think I can, I think I can ... ”: The interrelationships among self-assessed intelligence, self-concept, self-efficacy and the personality trait intellect in university students in Scotland and New Zealand. *Personality Individual Difference*, 43, 959–968.
- Pillis, E and Reardon, K. K. (2007). The influence of personality traits and persuasive messages on entrepreneurial intention: A cross-cultural comparison. *Career Development International*, 12, (4), 382-396.
- Pruett, M. (2012). Entrepreneurship education: Workshops and entrepreneurial intentions. *Journal of Education for Business*, 87, 94-101.
- Rauch, A., and Frese, M. (2007). Born to Be an Entrepreneur? Revisiting the Personality Approach to Entrepreneurship. In J. R. Baum, M. Frese , & R. A. Baron, *The Psychology of Entrepreneurship* (pp. 41–65). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Inc.

- Ridha, R.N. and Wahyu, B.P. (2017). Entrepreneurship intention in agricultural sector of young generation in Indonesia. *Asia Pacific Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 11, (1),76-89.
- Roberts, A., Chou, P., and Ching, A. (2010). Contemporary Trend in East Asia Higher Education: Disposition of International Students in Taiwan Universities. *Higher Education*, 59, 149-166.
- Ryckman, R. M. (2004). Theories of personality (8th ed.) Cited in Noraini binti et al (2015) Association between Personality Traits and Job Performance among Secondary School Teachers. *International Academic Research Journal of Social Science*, 1, (2), 1-6.
- Ryckman, R. M. (2000). *Theories of Personality*, 7th ed. Belmont, CA : Wadsworth/Thomson Learning.
- Shane, S. (2003). *A General Theory of Entrepreneurship: The Individual-Opportunity Nexus* . Aldershot, UK: Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Singh, G., and De Noble, A. F . (2003). Views on Self-Employment and Personality: An Exploratory Study. *Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship*, 8, (3), 265–281.
- Smallbone, D., and Welter, F. (2012). Entrepreneurship and institutional change in transition economies: The Commonwealth of Independent States, Central and Eastern Europe and China compared. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 24, (3-4), 21.
- Sun, Y., and Zhang, X.K. (2014). The path model of the relationship of personality traits, entrepreneurial self-efficacy, and entrepreneurial intention among college students. *Student Psychology Behaviour*, 12, 806–812.
- Thomas, A. S., and Mueller, S. L. (2000). A Case for Comparative Entrepreneurship: Assessing the Relevance of Culture. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 31, (2), 287-301.
- Thompson, E. R. (2009). Individual entrepreneurial intent: Construct clarification and development of an internationally reliable metric . *Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice* , 33, (3), 669–694.
- Tong, X. F., Tong, D. Y., and Loy, L. C. (2011). Factors influencing Entrepreneurial Intention among University Students. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanity Study*, 3, (1), 487-496
- Van Praag, C., and Ophem, H. (1995). Determinants of willingness and opportunity to start as an entrepreneur. *Kyklos*, 48: 513-540.
- Wall, G., and Mathiesom, A. (2006). *Tourism: Change, Impacts and Opportunities*. New York: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Wang, J.H., Chang, C.C., Yao, S.N., and Liang, C. (2016). The contribution of self-efficacy to the relationship between personality traits and entrepreneurial intention. *Higher Education*, 72, 1–16.
- Xu, Y., and Guo, F.C . (2015). The relationship among Entrepreneurial stress, entrepreneurial self-efficacy and entrepreneurial intention of Higher Vocational College Students. *Res. Higher Educ. Eng.*, 2, 164–168.
- Zahari, N. A. (2016). Personality traits and differences of generations: Do they affect the public servants' job performance? *Journal of Global Business and Social Entrepreneurship*, 2, (4), 20-30.
- Zhao, H., and Seibert, S. E. (2006). The Big Five personality dimensions and entrepreneurial status: A meta-analytical review. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 91,(2), 259-271.
- Zhao, H., Seibert, S. E., and Lumpkin, G. T. (2010). The relationship of personality to entrepreneurial intentions and performance: A meta-analytic review. *Journal of Management*, 36, (2), 381–404.